

**INTERCULTURAL AWARENESS, LANGUAGE LEARNING AUTONOMY,
LEARNING EXPERIENCES: A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING
STUDY ON SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE**

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Intercultural Awareness, Language Learning Autonomy, Learning Experiences: A Structural Equation Modeling Study on Sociolinguistic Competence

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Abstract

The goal of this study is to determine the best model for sociolinguistic competency in the Filipino language in Region XI public schools. A combination of descriptive, correlational, and casual comparative designs were employed in the study, and 400 respondents were selected through stratified random sampling using four questionnaires as the research tool. The study made use of a number of statistical methods, including multiple regression, Pearson product moment correlation, semantic equation modeling, and mean and standard deviation. The study found that, in contrast to the high degree of language learning autonomy, the level of intercultural awareness, learning experience, and sociolinguistic competence reached a moderate level. Additionally, there was a strong correlation between sociolinguistic competency and learning experience, intercultural awareness and sociolinguistic competence, and language learning autonomy and sociolinguistic competence. Because all of the indices that satisfied the established criteria were quite acceptable in comparison to the value of the most appropriate model, the study also found that the third model created was appropriate for sociolinguistic competency. Overall, the study's findings showed low levels of intercultural awareness, sociolinguistic competence, and language learning autonomy; this suggests that relationships related to society, culture, and language haven't received much attention and significance thus far. In order to raise awareness among students and knowledge advocates about the relationship between society, language, and culture that functioned as a pathway for everyone, the researchers strongly recommend that the research be carried out in the future.

Keywords: *intercultural awareness, language learning autonomy, learning experiences, sociolinguistic competence, semantic equational modeling*

Introduction

Language is a factor in communication in the application of the concept from the culture of origin to other aspects that require intellectual ability and equally focus on different areas of knowledge used in the development of sociolinguistic ability that may lead to inappropriate consequence (Ali Al Briki and Rahman Khan, 2019). Also causing difficulty in the development of sociolinguistic skills is the presence of insufficient knowledge acquired in the second language and awareness of other cultures, low interest in learning that is linked to the teaching and learning process as well as the readiness of the equipment designed to promote the knowledge gained (Gulomova, 2022). This in turn was agreed by Geçkin (2022) that the lack of this ability is the reason for the low level of interaction and the use of traditional teaching and learning methods.

Making sense of the concepts and levels of sociolinguistic ability raises cultural awareness and interaction with other members which by considering this ability in the linguistic aspect provides adequate and appropriate needs to others. another skill that applies the knowledge gained in processing ways and styles that can be used in any aspect as well as in other situations (Jumaniyozova and Rakhimova, 2022). In the study by Zakharova and Gulinov (2021), it was found that factors such as the first language, behavior, interest, and active participation in various academic activities not only within the classroom but also in applying knowledge to external experiences have a connection to linguistic and social abilities, which are encompassed by cultural context. This has led to each member in the processing of general knowledge becoming meaningful and taking steps that can be considered as individual development, particularly in the sociolinguistic ability in language.

In other areas, studies often focus on the application of linguistic knowledge to a specific and primary aspect, such as the use of words and their meanings. However, the use of linguistic knowledge in interactions with different types and categories of people, not only within the curricular context but also externally, coming from different cultures and social levels, is often overlooked. (Xamidullaevna, 2020). Therefore, it is suggested that contemporary researchers are warmly invited to address and further expand the exploration of the application of linguistic knowledge in the interaction of various people with different backgrounds, especially now that the level of individuals from different cultures and life purposes continues to rise (Afonina et al., 2021).

It can be considered that students' learning experiences play a significant role in shaping their sociolinguistic competence because the use of language and cultural aspects in communication and interaction stems from the knowledge acquired, which undergoes various steps and processes in the establishment of language concepts, thereby enhancing interest in this competence (Iwuchukwu & Iwuchukwu R. N 12-22). N 12-22). Furthermore, the promotion of various academic activities in the learning of students in a particular course or subject has a significant and meaningful impact on language use, which is adapted to the application and desired use of knowledge, as it can be considered that each individual comes from different cultural backgrounds that shape communicative abilities, particularly sociolinguistic competence. (Khodos at Hunt 154).

This study is anchored in Hymes' theory of Communicative Competence (1972) developed by Canale and Swain (1980), which states that the possession of linguistic competence goes through a specific step to be applied in any context of life, such as interacting with others. (Subandowo, 2022) and supported by three theories; the Grounded Developmental theory in Bennett's Development Model of Intercultural Sensitivity (1998) proves that there is a connection between intercultural awareness and sociolinguistic competence, which states that everyone has the opportunity to experience one or more languages, behaviors, and cultures that can be the foundation for division and misunderstanding (Iqbal, 2021); The Bioecological Theory of Human Development by Bronfenbrenner (2001) has four aspects; the first two aspects, called the microsystem and mesosystem, indicate that the decision-making in a specific event emphasizes whether it is beneficial not only to oneself but also to other aspects such as communication with others using language and connecting with others from different cultural backgrounds to promote the next step in personal change (Osher et al., 2020) and Kob's Experimental Learning theory (1978), which states that the use of knowledge construction within the classroom, applied through various processing methods such as collaborative work, analysis, and concept identification, among others, will lead to reflection as a step in sociolinguistic competence (Philominraj et al., 2020).

On the other hand, this study will directly benefit teachers who serve as a pathway to the application of linguistic concepts, which may include additional methods and styles on how to address a particular skill that is primarily used by most not only within the classroom but also in society, which is continuously changing over time, thereby developing the various communicative abilities of students. For the student, this study will serve as a medium to fully develop the sociolinguistic competence associated with the latest concepts in the field of education and further raise awareness of the use of linguistic knowledge with people from different cultural backgrounds.

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Research Questions

As a certainty, this study has questions that serve as a guide:

1. What is the level of students' intercultural awareness through: definitions and types of culture; cultural diversity and cultural dimensions; definitions and importance of intercultural awareness; and components in the development of intercultural awareness;
2. What is level of students' determination in language acquisition through: trust in the teacher; understanding of the teacher's role; and confidence in one's own abilities;
3. What is the level of students' learning experience through: cognitive aspects; ability to socialize; and presence of teaching;
4. What is level of sociolinguistic competence in Filipino through: respect; camaraderie; confidence; resourcefulness; and emotional stability;
5. Is there significant relationship between: intercultural awareness and sociolinguistic competence; determination in language acquisition and sociolinguistic competence; and learning experience and sociolinguistic competence;
6. Among the hypothesized model for the sociolinguistic competence of students in Filipino, which is the best fit model suit in the study?

Literature Review

Intercultural Awareness

The cultural background of the students has a big impact on intercultural awareness, which can lead to different actions in the classroom that can have either positive or negative results (Yurtsever and Dilara, 2021). According to Yu and Pirnazaroy (2020), this component is comprised of several categories, such as the types and meanings of culture that have been identified in research that can increase awareness of culture and its domains utilizing a variety of criteria. The diversity of culture and its dimensions centered on different styles and responses that also led to proper application based on previous research (Hill et al., 2020). On the other hand, the meaning and importance of intercultural awareness that emerged in the study indicating that the achievement of such capability contributes to the self (Iqbal, 2021). The components in the development of intercultural awareness that should be considered in relation to the conducted research which revealed the processing of steps to make interactions with people from different cultural backgrounds meaningful. (Yurtsever and Dilara, 2021).

Language Learning Autonomy

In order to be applicable in every circumstance, each piece of knowledge is applied to a particular one and goes through a suitable and appropriate procedure (Januin, 2007). Based on the research, it consists of three indicators: first, the trust in the teacher that emerged in the study, emphasizing the student at every step of teaching and learning within the classroom (Teimouri, Plonsky, and Tabandeh, 2022); second, the understanding of the teacher's role, which the research indicates as the student's trust in the teacher's role in conducting various active tasks if they are meaningful based on the study (Pedler, Suzanne & Yeigh, 2020); and lastly, the confidence in one's own ability, which the study proves as the student's self-strength related to participation and promotion of activities. (Akbari and Sahibzada, 2020).

Learning Experiences

The new curriculum currently in use offers pupils a variety of experiences that might result in either positive or bad consequences, as evidenced by three indicators (Wei, 2020). the existence of a cognitive component focused on the student's intellectual capacity, which was established in light of earlier research demonstrating that the ideas covered aid in the development of this component (Gu et al., 2021). On the other hand, the presence of social interaction ability, which examines and identifies the student's interaction with other members within the classroom while using the knowledge gained from the discussion, leading to the proper application of interventions according to the findings of the conducted study (Wu, 2023).The presence of teaching presence, which outlines a study where the teacher's performance within the classroom to identify those who should receive feedback is a pathway to improvement (Wang et al., 2021).

Sociolinguistic Competence

It can be regarded as one of the communicative competencies that concentrates on developing students' sociolinguistic ability, which is influenced by a number of factors, including their upbringing and their awareness of the language, including its structure (Huong & Ho, 2021). Research has indicated that respect is based on being realistic and sensitive in every use of language in particular situations (Sarimsakova, 2021), secondly, camaraderie, which refers to the interaction of students with others in a positive and good manner, has been a common outcome in past research (Kolsut, ad Szumilas, 2023); thirdly, confidence, which may depend on the results of other research, brings ease in any situation and promotes activities with enthusiasm and interest; fourthly, resourcefulness, which indicates being open to any opportunity on how to apply sufficient action to make the outcome beneficial (Sugiharto, 2021); lastly, emotional maturity, which has been highlighted in studies related to academic performance, focusing on appropriateness and excellence in responding according to the time or event (Afnita et al., 2021).

Methodology

Research Design

This research was conducted according to descriptive, correlational, and causal-comparative designs and by using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) in this study, it will strengthen the integrity and rigor of this research because the analysis will go through the steps of model specification, data collection, model estimation, model evaluation, and possible model modification. So, when the hypothesized model is rejected based on the goodness of fit statistics, an alternative model that fits the data needs to be created (Hidayat & Wulandari, 2022). This study was applied with the Structural Equation Modeling which will be used to obtain the best and most appropriate model for the study. According to Marcoulides et al., (2020), Semantic Equational Modeling (SEM) is related to a method that can unify complex path models with latent variables. Through this, the researcher can specify confirmatory factor analysis models, regression models, and complex path models.

On the other hand, statistical tools were used for data collection and estimation such as: Mean, which was used to determine the level of intercultural awareness, language acquisition decision, learning experience, and sociolinguistic competence; Pearson-r-Correlation, which was used to determine the significant relationship between the variables. Multiple Regression will be used to determine the significant influence of intercultural awareness, language acquisition decision, learning experience, and sociolinguistic competence in Filipino among Senior High School students. Finally, this study will be applied with the Structural Equation Modeling to obtain the best and most appropriate model for the study.

Respondents

In the study conducted by the researcher, Senior High School students from a public school were chosen. Four hundred students served as respondents in the research from a total of 1,678,856 students in various public secondary schools in Region XI. The respondents for the study will be selected from the divisions of the Region using the Raosoft application to ensure an accurate and appropriate number of data sources (Sulaiman et al., 2022). This was composed of the following: Division A in the Southern part with 56 respondents consisting of the Branches of Davao Occidental; Division B in the Western part composed of 159 respondents including Davao del Sur, Davao City, and the City of Digos; Division C in the Eastern part composed of the Branches of Davao Oriental, the City of Mati, and Igacos with 111 respondents; and Division D in the Northern part composed of the Branches of Davao del Norte and the City of Tagum. Compostela Valley and the City of Panabo, consisting of 74 respondents. In order to identify the number of

respondents who would provide high credibility and a degree of truth in the data, which would lead to a rich and thorough coverage of the study's phenomena, the aforementioned study participants were chosen using the stratified random sampling method. (Nguyen and others, 2021).

On the other hand, the respondents of this research were the students in Grades 11 and 12. The researcher chose these grade levels because they are considered the final stage of basic education and are focused on specific subjects related to society, language, and culture, as well as the readiness to apply the knowledge gained in various subjects that encompass different learning experiences. On the other hand, the other grade levels were not included in this research because the students are focused only on the core subjects and the subjects related to culture and language have not yet been specified. Additionally, private schools were not involved in this study because they have different systems of knowledge dissemination and the processing of applying knowledge within the classroom, unlike public schools where each step, system, and approach to imparting knowledge to students is similar.

Instrument

The study used questionnaires adapted from various studies developed by the researcher using the focused language, which underwent extensive validation such as correcting appropriate translations, effective contextualization of selected questions, and maintaining the proper flow of meaning of the statements or questions from the adapted questionnaires of previous studies to ensure that the respondents' answers to the actual and final survey questions are accurate and meaningful. The research instrument is divided into four parts: first, the intercultural awareness adapted from the research of Yurtsever and Dilara (2021), which consists of four parts and 20 items; second, the language achievement decision derived from the research of Januin and Sabah (2007) with three parts and 30 items; third, the learning experience based on the study of Wei et al. (1-12) with three parts and 38 items; finally, the sociolinguistic competence adapted from the study of Huong and Hoa (2021) which consists of five aspects and 50 items.

On the other hand, to determine the appropriate and proper measurement of the level of intercultural awareness, language acquisition decision, learning experience, and sociolinguistic competence, the researcher used a 5-point Likert Scale anchored between the semantic differential pairs "Strongly Agree or Strongly Disagree," which corresponded to the following scale; a mean range of 4.20-5.00 has a descriptive level of very high, with the interpretation that it is always demonstrated. The mean range of 3.40-4.19 indicates a high level, meaning the assessment is often demonstrated. The 2.50-3.39 range of the mean corresponds to a descriptive level classified as moderate, with the interpretation that the assessment was demonstrated occasionally. While the range of the Mean from 1.80-2.59 indicates a low assessment that is rarely demonstrated. Those with a mean range of 1.00-1.79 have a descriptive level classified as very low, with the interpretation that the assessment was never demonstrated.

Furthermore, the instruments used were reviewed by six experts and received an overall score of 4.4. The pilot testing and the reliability of the instruments were also conducted using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient, which showed in the analysis that intercultural awareness achieved good reliability (0.74); language achievement decision achieved (0.97); learning experience (0.79); and sociolinguistic competence (0.98), indicating acceptable and good reliability results.

Procedure

This study will be conducted with consideration of the ethical protocols and guidelines implemented by the University of Mindanao committee. The researcher ensured formal consent from the participants involved in the study and considered the appropriateness of the selected participants. On the other hand, after the thorough validation of the research instruments used, a certificate of approval was granted by UMERC to conduct data collection from the selected respondents with Protocol no. UMERC-2024-272. This is a sign that the researcher followed an appropriate and correct process in valuing the factors in using the respondents' identities through their answers in the study.

Ethical Considerations

However, this study will be conducted with consideration of the ethical protocols and guidelines implemented by the University of Mindanao committee. The researcher ensured formal consent from the participants involved in the study and considered the appropriateness of the selected participants, as well as the potential risks they might encounter, including various aspects such as physical, psychological, and social. The consent and agreement of the study sample were emphasized, particularly the importance of data processing, highlighting the rights of the respondents.

All participants in the study were not forced and willingly answered the questionnaire. However, they voluntarily spend their time and effort answering the research without any threat of intimidation. They cannot be deprived of their legal freedoms and rights due to their participation in this research. All data collected from the study participants will remain confidential, and the researcher values the identity of each respondent in the study.

The researcher fully accepted the refusal of participants to engage in the study. The researcher also clarified that there would be no penalties imposed on students who do not participate in the study. The researcher also ensured that the data collection equipment, especially the used ones, were stored in a proper location. Therefore, any data obtained from the respondents will remain confidential, and their identities will be valued by the researcher.

Results and Discussion

The data collected from the respondents' completed questionnaires was presented, examined, and interpreted in this section of the study. The presentation was in line with the particular queries that were raised in light of the study's goals.

Intercultural Awareness

Table 1. *Intercultural Awareness*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
definitions and types of culture	0.83	3.38	moderate
cultural diversity and its boundaries	0.79	3.36	moderate
meanings and importance of intercultural awareness	0.64	3.41	high
components for developing intercultural awareness	0.84	3.30	moderate
Overall	0.57	3.36	moderate

The level of intercultural awareness of public Senior High School students, which was measured and interpreted using the mean score. Table 1 shows an overall mean score of 3.26 and a standard deviation of 0.57, described as moderate in promoting the intercultural awareness of students. This result is based on the combined results of four indicators: definitions and types of culture with a mean score of 3.38 and a standard deviation of 0.83, cultural diversity and its boundaries with a mean score of 3.36 and a standard deviation of 0.79, and components for developing intercultural awareness with a mean score of 3.30 and a standard deviation of 0.84, both of which are described as being rarely focused on by students. On the other hand, the indicators of the meanings and importance of intercultural awareness received a high mean score of 3.41 and a standard deviation of 0.64, which means that students often focus on them in their learning.

Based on the overall results indicating that the intercultural awareness of Senior High School students was demonstrated at times because it illustrated culture in various aspects, the importance of having knowledge of complex cultures, and the proper examination of one's own cultural identity in most instances. This outcome aligns with the study by Yurtsever and Dilara (2021), which found that emphasizing the student's cultural background significantly influences their learning. Therefore, it can lead to either a high or low level of application in understanding various concepts in each school discussion. (Tural at Cubukcu 2021).

Language Learning Autonomy

Table 2. *Language Learning Autonomy*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
trust in the teacher	0.71	3.41	high
understanding of the teacher's role	0.66	3.40	high
confidence in one's own abilities	0.71	3.41	high
Overall	0.53	3.41	high

In the aspect of language learning autonomy of Senior High School students, based on Table 2 which has an overall mean score of 3.41 and a standard deviation of 0.53 indicating high. This consists of three indicators; trust in the teacher with a mean score of 3.41 and a standard deviation of 0.71, which means high, understanding of the teacher's role with a mean score of 3.40 and a standard deviation of 0.66, indicating high, and confidence in one's own abilities with a mean score of 3.41 and a standard deviation of 0.71, which means high.

The data that emerged prove that students who often show readiness in finding their own ways of practicing and seeking help from the teacher, are aware of their success in language learning which depends on what the teacher does in class, and believe that the role of a teacher is to point out the problems. This result aligns with the idea of Januin (2007) that each knowledge applied in a specific situation undergoes a proper and appropriate process to be used in various experiences. It was also proven in the study by Chong and Reinders (2022) that the use of analysis in a particular experience or any situation provides a proper and appropriate mechanism to continue the steps in the next process to create a new project.

Learning Experiences

Table 3. *Learning Experiences*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
cognitive aspect	0.73	3.35	moderate
social interaction ability	0.69	3.36	moderate
teaching presence	0.67	3.42	high
Overall	0.54	3.38	moderate

The results obtained based on Table 3 from the study on the learning experiences of Senior High School students have an overall mean score of 3.38 and a standard deviation of 0.54, which is described as moderate. This is comprised of three indicators; the cognitive aspect with a mean score of 3.35 and a standard deviation of 0.73, which is described as moderate, as well as the indicator of social interaction ability with a mean score of 3.36 and a standard deviation of 0.69. Meanwhile, the teaching presence indicator received a

mean score of 3.42 and a standard deviation of 0.67, which is interpreted as high.

In relation to the results obtained, it indicates that the students occasionally received guidance from the teacher during discussions while engaging in group work, each member rarely actively participated in open discussions within the classroom, and there was seldom any new knowledge gained from the learning activities to solve problems. The study's findings are related to the concept developed by Zhao (2024), which indicates that the promotion of various experiences gained by students in using the new curriculum currently may lead to negative outcomes if not properly established. Furthermore, the findings of the study are also centered on the research conducted by Onu, Pradhan, and Mbohwa (2024), which indicates that focusing on the learning experience has become a significant factor in the promotion of various concepts for students because it is important and necessary for everyone to fulfill.

Sociolinguistic Competence

Table 4. Sociolinguistic Competence

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
respect	0.86	3.35	moderate
camaraderie	0.67	3.33	moderate
confidence	0.78	3.32	moderate
resourcefulness	0.67	3.37	moderate
emotional maturity	0.73	3.37	moderate
Overall	0.49	3.35	moderate

Based on Table 4, which includes sociolinguistic competence, the overall mean score is 3.35 with a standard deviation of 0.49, indicating that the students' competence in this area is only moderate. This is a combined result using five indicators: respect, with a mean score of 3.35 and a standard deviation of 0.86, described as moderate, similar to the indicators; camaraderie with a mean score of 3.33 and a standard deviation of 0.67, confidence 3.32 and a standard deviation of 0.78, , resourcefulness with a mean score of 3.37 and a standard deviation of 0.67, and emotional maturity with a mean score of 3.37 and a standard deviation of 0.73.

The results indicate that the students do not always value the contributions of others and support other people, whether verbally or non-verbally. They often address various situations in a systematic manner and occasionally expand their awareness using different experiences gained from completed situations. Such outcomes directly align with the idea of Huong and Ho (2021) that achieving sociolinguistic competence is not easily attained because it involves various factors that can affect its application, such as the culture one is accustomed to and awareness of the language, including its structure.

Furthermore, it is also clear from the findings of Geckin's study (2022) that the reason why the promotion of sociolinguistic competence is still prevalent today is due to the lack of this competence and the low level of interaction and use of traditional teaching and learning methods.

Significant Relationship between Intercultural Awareness and Sociolinguistic Competence

Table 5.1. Significant Relationship between Intercultural Awareness and Sociolinguistic Competence

<i>Intercultural Awareness</i>	<i>Sociolinguistic Competence</i>					<i>Overall</i>
	<i>respect</i>	<i>camaraderie</i>	<i>confidence</i>	<i>resourcefulness</i>	<i>emotional maturity</i>	
definitions and types of culture	.104*	.096	.055	.053	.085	.121*
	.042	.061	.281	.302	.098	.019
cultural diversity and its boundaries	.064	.030	.020	.068	.065	.075
	.216	.560	.692	.189	.209	.145
meanings and importance of intercultural awareness	.142**	.158**	.067	.038	.035	.136**
	.006	.002	.190	.459	.499	.008
components for developing intercultural awareness	.166**	.144**	-.024	.037	-.003	.099
	.001	.005	.638	.473	.947	.053
Overall	.162**	.144**	.038	.068	.062	.146**
	.001	.005	.466	.189	.225	.004

Table 5.1 shows the significant relationship between intercultural awareness and sociolinguistic competence with an overall result of an r-value of .146 and a corresponding p-value of .000 (significant), which is much lower than the 0.05 significance level set in this study. Therefore, the hypothesis should be rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between intercultural awareness and the sociolinguistic competence of the students. This simply means that when students have high intercultural awareness, they also have high sociolinguistic competence.

The results of this table show that there is a significant relationship between intercultural awareness and sociolinguistic competence. This indicates that possessing one of the communicative competencies, such as sociolinguistic competence, requires sufficient awareness of the intercultural aspect to make the outcome meaningful in any context to which it is applied. This statement focuses on the idea of Jumaniyozova and Rakhimova (2022, that the interpretation of concepts and levels of sociolinguistic competence enhances cultural awareness and interaction with other members in the linguistic aspect across various skills, applying the knowledge gained in

processing methods and styles that can be used in any aspect as well as in other situations. This result aligns with Gashi idea (2021), which posits that intercultural awareness serves as a factor that should be emphasized in the use of sociolinguistic competence so that the goal of having proper and extensive interactions with others, paying attention to good relationships, and environments aligned with general preferences is given meaning.

Significant Relationship between Language Learning Autonomy and Sociolinguistic Competence

Table 5.2. Significant Relationship between Language Learning Autonomy and Sociolinguistic Competence

Language Learning Autonomy	Sociolinguistic Competence					Overall
	respect	camaraderie	confidence	resourcefulness	emotional maturity	
trust in the teacher	.141**	.095	-.001	.128*	.108*	.142**
	.006	.064	.979	.012	.035	.005
Understand-ing of the teacher's role	.102*	.096	.081	.118*	.093	.148**
	.047	.061	.114	.021	.069	.004
confidence in one's own abilities	.175**	.173**	.117*	.158**	.128*	.228**
	.001	.001	.022	.002	.012	.000
Overall	.184**	.160**	.085	.177**	.144**	.227**
	.000	.002	.096	.001	.005	.000

Table 5.2 shows the significant relationship between language learning autonomy and the sociolinguistic competence of senior high school students, with an overall r-value of .227 and a p-value of .000 (significant) well below the .05 significance level set in this study. Therefore, the hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was accepted, indicating a significant relationship between language acquisition decisions and the sociolinguistic competence of the students.

The results of this study align with the ideas of Abd Rahman et al. (2022), who demonstrated that each acquired linguistic concept is freely accepted based on the academic needs of the student. This acceptance has led to its application in various contexts, not only for personal use but also within the society that encompasses different cultures using the language. However, this process undergoes scrutiny and evaluation, which can only be utilized in specific situations to make the promotion of sociolinguistic competence meaningful.

Furthermore, in the study conducted by Herawati (2021), it was realized that the reason behind the creativity of students who analyze each acquired knowledge, leading to decisions that allowed them to explore linguistic concepts, paved the way for the development of communicative abilities, particularly in the sociolinguistic aspect.

Significant Relationship between Learning Experiences and Sociolinguistic Competence

Table 5.3. Significant Relationship between Learning Experiences and Sociolinguistic Competence

Learning Experiences	Sociolinguistic Competence					Overall
	respect	camaraderie	confidence	resourcefulness	emotional maturity	
cognitive aspect	.121*	.220**	.187**	.121*	.113*	.229**
	.019	.000	.000	.018	.028	.000
social interaction ability	.161**	.180**	.241**	.141**	.078	.245**
	.002	.000	.000	.006	.129	.000
teaching presence	.181**	.183**	.219**	.255**	.240**	.325**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Overall	.196**	.250**	.276**	.218**	.182**	.340**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Table 5.3 presents the significant relationship between learning experience and sociolinguistic competence, which recorded a total r-value of .340 and a p-value of .000 (significant) well below the .05 significance level set in this study. Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis, which posits a significant relationship between learning experience and students' learning experience.

The results indicate that the learning experiences and sociolinguistic competence have a sufficiently significant relationship with each other. This means that the various learning experiences within the classroom have appropriately and correctly contributed to the development of sociolinguistic competence in the Filipino language. As a connection, the results obtained based on the collected data align with the concept developed by Zakharova and Gulinov (2021), which found in their study that the first language, behavior, interest, and active engagement in various academic activities not only within the classroom but also in applying knowledge to external experiences have a relationship with linguistic and social competence.

Furthermore, the same findings were observed in the study by Khodos and Hunt (2022), which highlighted the promotion of various academic activities in student learning. This was also confirmed in the study by Alfonina et al. (2022), which emphasized the need to address and expand the search for the application of linguistic knowledge in interactions with different people from diverse backgrounds, especially now that the levels of interaction are continuously rising due to various cultures and lifestyles.

Significant Relationship of Intercultural Awareness, Language Learning Autonomy and Learning Experiences on Sociolinguistic Competence

Table 6. Significant Relationship of Intercultural Awareness, Language Learning Autonomy and Learning Experiences on Sociolinguistic Competence

Variable	B	β	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.864		8.862	.000
Intercultural Awareness	.069	.080	1.629	.104
Language Learning Autonomy	.107	.116	2.254	.025
Learning Experiences	.262	.291	5.718	.000
R	.370			
R ²	.137			
ΔR	.130			
F	19.857			
ρ	.000			

Table 6 describes the significant influence of intercultural awareness and language learning autonomy, learning experiences in sociolinguistic competence, which has been proven based on the collected data. The results show a significant relationship between each variable, with an F-value of 19.857, R-value of .370, R² of .137, and a p-value of .000, which is much lower than the .05 significance level set in this study.

The significant aspects identified based on the analysis of the collected data are focused on the ideas, concepts, and outcomes of previous studies. Thus, the selected students who served as respondents in this study were clearly given the relationship between culture and language that can be used in shaping sociolinguistic competence. This aligns with the study by Algouzi and Atamna (2021), which found that the presence of intercultural awareness requires sufficient knowledge related to language and culture, comprising sociolinguistic competence. Each person's experience is considered complex, as it demonstrates the planned and derived abilities attained towards a broader understanding.

Likewise, it can be said that the students involved in this study have the ability to maintain sociolinguistic competence through various experiences in learning language concepts, which is related to the study by Iwuchukwu and Iwuchukwu RN (2018). They have proven that students' learning experiences play a significant role in shaping sociolinguistic competence because the use of language and cultural aspects in communication and interaction stems from the knowledge acquired through various steps and processes in establishing language concepts, thereby enhancing interest in this competence.

Overall Results of Goodness of Fit Measures among the Three Models

Table 7. Overall Results of Goodness of Fit Measures among the Three Models

Model	P-value (>0.05)	CMIN/DF (0<value<2)	GFI (>0.95)	CFI (>0.95)	NFI (>0.95)	TLI (>0.95)	RMSEA (<0.05)	P-close (>0.05)
1	.000	5.508	.857	.754	.718	.703	.109	.000
2	.000	5.397	.865	.766	.730	.711	.108	.000
3	.817	.706	.992	1.00	.984	1.014	.000	.998

Legend: CMIN/DF – Chi Square/Degrees of Freedom, GFI – Goodness of Fit Index, RMSEA – Root Mean Square of Error Approximation, CFI – Comparative Fit Index, NFI – Normed Fit Index, TLI – Tucker-Lewis Index

In a thorough analysis, three variables are significant in sociolinguistic competence; intercultural awareness with a B-value of .069 and a β -value of .080, a t-value of 1.629 and a p-value of .104 (significant); language acquisition decision with a B-value of .107 and a β -value of .080, a t-value of 1.629 and a p-value of .025 (significant); learning experience with a B-value of .262 and a β -value of .291, a t-value of 5.718 and a p-value of .000. (significant).

Figure 1. Hypothesized Model 1

Figure 1 shows Hypothesized Model 1, which illustrates the direct relationship of exogenous variables: intercultural awareness, language acquisition decision, and learning experience, and the model's relationship with the endogenous variable of students' sociolinguistic competence. In the analysis of Model 1, using the goodness of fit indices: the Chi-Square divided by the degrees of freedom (CMIN/DF) is .5.508; the Normed Fit Index (NFI) is .718; the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) is .703; the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is .754; the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) is .857; the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is .109; and the P of Close Fit (P-close) is .000.

Regression Weights of the Three Models

Table 8. Regression Weights of the Three Models

<i>Exogenous Variables to Endogenous Variable</i>			
<i>Model</i>	<i>Intercultural Awareness</i>	<i>Language Learning Autonomy</i>	<i>Learning Experiences</i>
1	.068NS	.116NS	.442***
2	.066NS	.126NS	.443***
3	.057NS	.104NS	.294**

Based on the framework, the exogenous and endogenous variables from the developed Structural model. From the data in Table 8, it is clearly shown that the learning experience achieved a high result (beta = 0.442), followed by intercultural awareness (beta = 0.68) and language achievement decision (beta = 0.116). However, in Table 7, all the indices did not reach the acceptable number found in the appendix. Therefore, this is a weak and inadequate model based on the goodness of fit criteria along with CMIN/DF > 2, GFI, CFI, TLI < 0.95, RMSEA > 0.05, and P-close < 0.05.

The Hypothesized Model 2 is presented in Table 3, which shows the direct relationship of the exogenous variables: intercultural awareness, language acquisition decision, and learning experience, and the model's relationship with the endogenous variable, the sociolinguistic competence of the students. As an emphasis on Model 2, using the goodness of fit indices: Chi-Square divided by degrees of freedom (CMIN/DF) is .5.397; the Normed Fit Index (NFI) is .730; the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) is .711; the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is .766; the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) is .865; the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is .108; and the P of Close Fit (P-close) is .000.

Figure 2. Hypothesized Model 2

The exogenous and endogenous variables according to Table 8 from the developed Structural model clearly show that the learning experience achieved a high result (beta = 0.443), followed by language acquisition decision (beta = 0.126) and intercultural awareness (beta = 0.066). However, in Table 7, all the indices did not reach the acceptable number found in the appendix. Therefore, this is a weak and inadequate model based on the goodness of fit criteria along with CMIN/DF > 2, GFI, CFI, TLI < 0.95, and RMSEA > 0.05 as well as P-close < 0.05.

The analysis of Model 3 as shown using the goodness of fit indices: Chi-Square divided by degrees of freedom (CMIN/DF) is .706; the Normed Fit Index (NFI) is .984; the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) is 1.1014; the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is 1.00; the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) is .992; the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is .000; and the P of Close Fit (Pclose) is .998. The goodness of fit result of model 3 is highly acceptable because all the indices met the established standards against the obtained fit value of the model. These indices meet the requirements of goodness of fit measures. Moreover, this is an indicator that model 3 is a very good model suitable for this study.

On the other hand, the exogenous and endogenous variables according to Table 8 from the developed Structural model clearly show that the learning experience achieved a high result (beta = 0.294), followed by language acquisition decision (beta = 0.104) and intercultural awareness (beta = 0.057). However, in Table 7, all the indices reached and are acceptable as shown in the appendix. Therefore, this is a strong and acceptable model based on the goodness of fit criteria along with CMIN/DF > 2, GFI, CFI, TLI < 0.95, RMSEA > 0.05, and P-close < 0.05.

Figure 3. Hypothesized Model 3

Conclusions

There is a generally moderate level of intercultural awareness, learning experience, and sociolinguistic competence, indicating that both students and learning facilitators have not significantly advanced in the processing. Therefore, it is suggested to strengthen the consideration of social, cultural, and linguistic relations not only in internal activities but also in tasks that require greater attention and intervention. Teachers are also urged to assign group projects or other cooperative assignments where each student is responsible for their own activities. To further encourage kids to participate in the activities given to them, each group should receive feedback on their work and be recognized for the most innovative work.

The overall outcomes of the choice to attain a high degree of language competence also demonstrated it. The researcher recommends that teachers support methods that offer thorough knowledge and effective linguistic approaches to further enhance students' interest and develop their ability to validate the appropriateness of applying linguistic concepts in any context, even though its level was only high and did not reach the highest level. This will allow for the full realization of an extensive and comprehensive understanding of linguistic concepts.

Intercultural awareness and sociolinguistic competence have been shown to have a strong correlation in the relationship of factors, which is consistent with Bennett's grounded developmental theory (1998). According to this idea, successful relationships, personal growth, and the improvement of other abilities are ensured when linguistic competence is applied effectively and one is sensitive to the results of any activity in various parts of society, including culture. The choice to learn a language and develop sociolinguistic competence is also pertinent to Bronfenbrenner's Bioecological Theory of Human Development (2001) which explains the relationship between assessing the likelihood of picking up skills or knowledge that can be applied to any situation in life, including interacting with people through language.

On the other hand, this study also proves that there is a significant relationship between learning experience and sociolinguistic competence. Therefore, this encompasses Kob's (2014) theory of Experimental Learning, which indicates that the consideration of learning focuses on and understands the outcomes of any project where language serves as a medium for interaction and engagement among members from diverse cultural backgrounds and language usage. Overall, the theory of Communicative Competence by Hymes (1972) is appropriate and correct as the basis for this research because, according to the theory, there is a relationship between achieving language knowledge, such as awareness of cultural aspects, critical examination of each linguistic concept experienced, and learning it. A specific ability cannot be realized without valuing awareness of different cultures, which can be used to determine which linguistic concepts should be applied based on the learning experiences promoted by the student

In other parts, the use of a structural benchmark model has strengthened this study because the analysis follows the sequential process of the specific model. Among the three models examined, model 3 has a consistent index and indicates that the data is the most suitable. Therefore, it was recognized as the most suitable model. The goodness of fit result of model 3 is highly acceptable because all the indices met the set standards against the obtained value of the most suitable model.

Overall, this study found that the level of intercultural awareness, language acquisition determination, and sociolinguistic competence is low. Therefore, this is a significant indication that up to the present, the understanding of the relationship between society, culture, and language is not strong and not given much importance, which means that it is not yet highly regarded and valued by most, especially in relation to the Filipino language. Because of this, it is very important as a Filipino to further develop and use it at the appropriate times. The researcher sincerely and wholeheartedly suggests that the research be continued in the future and that steps be taken to raise awareness not only among students but also among advocates of knowledge regarding the relationship between society, language, and

culture, which serves as a pathway for all.

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